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MODELLING AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DEGRADATION PROCESSES IN HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYMER FUEL CELLS

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Degradation of HT-PEMFCs is one of the main barriers limiting their widespread deployment. To extend their useful lifetime, it is essential to understand the contributions of the different degradation mechanisms. A new combined model to simulate the most important degradation processes under normal operating conditions has been developed. This model includes the processes taking place in the catalytic layer (corrosion of the carbon support, surface oxidation of Pt particles, Ostwald ripening and agglomeration of Pt particles) as well as the phosphoric acid (PA) loss from the membrane.

Firstly, the catalytic layer degradation starts with the oxidation processes on the Pt particles, which promote the corrosion of the carbon support[1]. Secondly, Pt nanoparticles naturally tend to agglomerate into larger particles to reduce the surface energy in two ways[2] as it is shown in Figure 1. On the one hand, Pt particles are dissolved into Pt^{2+} ions in the ionomer phase and then they are deposited in larger particles. This phenomenon, called Ostwald ripening, is more pronounced for smaller particles due to their high Gibbs free energy. On the other hand, neighboring Pt particles sinter into larger ones. The Pt agglomeration results in an increase of the particle size in the catalyst layer and a decrease of the overall effective area of Pt, thus reducing its catalytic capacity. These phenomena are strongly interrelated, since Pt oxidation assists in the carbon corrosion, which boost the detachment and agglomeration of the Pt particles. Furthermore, carbon corrosion depends on the mean radius of the particles. Lastly, in a PA-doped PBI membrane, there are free PA molecules that can migrate to other components or even outside the fuel cell, leading to a decrease in performance. Among PA loss mechanisms, the removal of PA excess at the beginning of the lifetime is the dominant phenomenon[3] and has therefore been included in this model.

Some parameters of the degradation processes are difficult to know experimentally and are usually taken as fitting parameters. Therefore, a method based on genetic algorithms[4] has been developed to characterize these parameters according to the evolution of the polarization curve of a fuel cell over time. These parameters can be used to predict the long term degradation of the device.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the particle growth mechanism for a) Ostwald ripening and b) Pt particle agglomeration. The blue and green spheres show respectively the initial and final particle size state.

References

- [1] N. Macauley, D.D. Papadias, J. Fairweather, et al. *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 165 (2018) F3148-F3160.
- [2] A. Kregar, A. Kravos and T. Kastrasnik. *Fuel Cells* 20 (2020) 487-498.
- [3] H.L. Lin, Y. S. Hsieh, C.W. Chiu, T. L. Yu and L. C. Chen. *J. Power Sources* 193 (2009) 170-174.
- [4] R. Losantos, M. Montiel, R. Mustata, F. Zorrilla and L. Valiño. *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 47 (2022) 4814-4826.